

USING A REFLECTIVE APPROACH TO LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: This article discusses the reflective approach, which stands out among many approaches in that it requires its own logical approach. In addition, it discusses the aims and objectives of this approach, its main ideas, and the effectiveness it brings to learners and teachers. In other words, this method of learning leads to the positive development of many skills in the teacher, and they can fully teach what they have learned to the students.

Key words: Innovating, approach, fundamental ideas, critical ideas, assembling, surveys, methodological devices.

As everyone knows, the field of education and its methodology is developing and growing day by day. As people and the world develop, they always strive to reach the pinnacle of knowledge. Along this arduous journey, they are constantly innovating, coming up with new methods, approaches and ideas. One such innovation is the Reflective approach. Naturally, when talking about the reflective approach, the first thing that comes to people's minds is - what is the reflective approach and what are its purposes and methods? For such cases, some information about this approach is provided below. The reflective approach is closely related to reflective teaching and requires an explanation of reflective teaching in the first place.

Reflective teaching - entails assessing one's alignment with real classroom practice before, during, and after a course is taught, as well as one's fundamental ideas about teaching and learning. Reflective teachers consider their instruction critically and seek out examples of successful instruction.

In this teaching method, most teachers use their critical thinking skills. For instance, it could be a group of students candidly talking about the difficulties they encountered during test preparation, or it could entail a student and tutor having one-on-one sessions in which the tutor guides the student's learning process with questions. This means that the lessons are not only about education and learning, but also talk about what the students did during this time and what mistakes they encountered. And the teacher comes to a conclusion about the situation in which the student is ready for the events and what he will do next. Along with this, even students are taught to think logically. The ability to think critically is crucial for education. It supports pupils' ability to reason logically and analytically. Furthermore, it motivates pupils to make real decisions and consider all relevant

factors when resolving issues. Students that engage in critical thinking in the classroom are able to think more broadly. As everything has a purpose, reflective teaching has several purposes.

Purposes:

- ✍ *to deepen comprehension of the process of teaching and learning.*
- ✍ *to increase one's range of tactical choices when teaching languages.*
- ✍ *To improve the standard of instruction and learning.*
- ✍ *Reflective educators strive to become better educators.*

Based on these goals, we can say that such an approach helps not only learners but also teachers to improve their many skills. For example:

- ✓ Compile details about everything that is happening in a language course.
- ✓ Identify any confusing aspects of the process of teaching and learning.
- ✓ Find others who are interested in the reflective teaching approach and work together with them
- ✓ Select and hone questions related to your instruction that merit more research.
- ✓ Make thoughtful adjustments to the responses and behaviors of teaching and learning
- ✓ Discuss new findings with educators who are interested in reflective practice.
- ✓ Find resources that could aid in providing clarification on the questions being asked.

In addition, there are a number of methodological devices of the reflective approach, the order in which they are used will be explained one by one. Furthermore, there are a number of methodological devices of the reflective approach, the order in which they are used will be explained one by one.

The main resources used by reflective educators. Some instruments for reflective use and some tools for teaching reflection:

✓ **1.Methods of assembling**

There are different ways to collect things. Some rely on non-permanent components such as bolts, screws or clamps to allow for maintenance and disassembly, while others use permanent components such as welding, glue or rivets. Such considerations are widely used not only in technical fields, but also in methodology. For this, first of all, all the information and terms related to the subject being studied are collected and then turned into a whole lesson for learning.

✓ **2.Information**

Receiving input—also referred to as stimulus—from the surroundings through a variety of senses is the first step in the process. After then, the input is described and kept in memory, from which it can be retrieved as needed. It is said that the brain or mind is similar to a computer that can process data from its surroundings.

✓ **3. Formative comments from students**

Additionally, feedback can be summative or formative. Formative feedback is when students are given more chances to practice or turn in their work after receiving it. Summative assessments are given to students at the conclusion of the learning process in order to provide them a general evaluation of their progress.

✓ **4. Five-minut sheets**

One of the many procrastination strategies used in cognitive behavioral therapy is the 5-minute rule. By following the five-minute rule, you give yourself a time limit of five minutes to accomplish whatever it is you would normally avoid completing.

✓ **5. Surveys for teaching assessments**

It's a method for gathering precise data through questioning in order to reach a conclusion and make critical judgments by making a connection to the actual circumstance. By guaranteeing that students participate actively, the survey is a technique that increases the effectiveness of learning. Questionnaires known as teacher surveys are employed to collect input from educators. Surveys can be distributed using software that is made to administer surveys in accordance with best practices, pen and paper, or Google Forms.

✓ **6. Questionaries**

A question is an issue, topic, or thing that has to be thought about. The fairness of his process was called into question by his judgment. Is this really what we want, we wonder? The main purpose of asking questions is to get information from the person you are speaking to by letting them know what the speaker (or writer) needs to know. A minor variation is the show question, which asks the addressee to provide information that the speaker already knows.

✓ **7. Journals of dialogues**

Many schools employ dialogue journals as a means of communication between teachers and students to enhance the learning environment by encouraging writing in a non-evaluative setting, sharing ideas and interests, and increasing student involvement. Many schools employ dialogue journals as a means of communication between teachers and students to enhance the learning

environment by encouraging writing in a non-evaluative setting, sharing ideas and interests, and increasing student involvement.

✓ **8. Composed remarks**

To be created from a variety of sources: The two major elements of air are nitrogen and oxygen. Members of the public, physicians, professors, and senators make up the committee. During job interviews, written exams are frequently used to assess an applicant's communication abilities. Writing a sample letter, essay, or press release is typically required for the communication skills written test, depending on the position you are applying for and the interviewer's preferences.

Effective language use in an EFL environment is now more closely associated with comprehending and using language that is acceptable for communicative contexts within particular sociocultural boundaries than it is with grammatical or linguistic precision. Within this focus, fostering students' intercultural competence has emerged as a key learning objective, a research topic, and discuss. In fact, the issue that still has to be resolved is how to provide students the intercultural competencies they need to interact effectively in a variety of cross-cultural contexts. This research tries to address this topic by proposing an intercultural training strategy that encourages students to think on and perform communicative actions, ultimately equipping them with practical knowledge and abilities. Creating an interactive learning environment is another goal of this kind of training, where instructors and students participate in a shared learning environment where meaning is negotiated. It is important to note that the main focus of this training procedure is students' reflection on language use in a particular context. This essay outlines the requirements for this reflection, including its elements and the teacher's responsibility. Additionally, it offers a series of communication exercises to support teachers in using this training strategy in their classrooms.

Knowledge refers to information, facts, and understanding acquired through learning or experience. It encompasses awareness and comprehension of various subjects, concepts, theories, principles, and practices. Skills, on the other hand, are the abilities to perform specific tasks effectively and efficiently. They are developed through practice, training, and experience. Skills can be categorized into different types such as technical skills (related to specific tasks or functions), soft skills (interpersonal and communication skills), cognitive skills (thinking and problem-solving abilities), and transferable skills (applicable across different contexts).

In general, the reflective approach can be used effectively and efficiently not only in language learning, but also in all areas of the educational system. This will help students achieve great success in meaningful learning.

References:

1. Reflective approach in English language teaching. Ishonqulov Sh.U. Article. 2022
2. Incultural treating in language learning: A reflective approach. Dr Zineb Djoub. Article. 2019.
3. What is the difference between knowledge and confidence?(Article)

<https://www.quora.com/What-is-the-difference-between-knowledge-and-confidence>

4. What is the term for the ability to do something or act.(Article)

<https://brainly.com/question/44590184>

